

EMOTION TAPPING

DESIGN FOR EMOTION ASSISTIVE RESEARCH ACTIVITY TOOL

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ABSTRACT

This research forms the basis of knowledge for the Emotion Tapping Chart, which is meant to be an aid for design practitioners in their efforts to create products which are more emotionally attuned with the needs of the end user. This helpful evaluative matrix is meant to be an aid and is an attempt to make the benefits of designing for emotion more accessible for the average design practitioner. In doing so, this research ultimately proposes to bridge the gap between theory and design practice. This study utilized structured interviews to understand and discover the needs of the modern design practitioner. Simultaneously, an expansive literature review was conducted covering contemporary Emotional Design Research, as well as many peripheral fields of study. Analysis of the data yields a framework mapping the research methods of design practitioners onto the Desmet model of product emotion (2008).

Keywords: Design for Emotion, User Product Interaction, Emotion Psychology, Research Methods, User Research.

INTRODUCTION

The gap between the realms of research and practice is often talked about as fundamental issue in design (Norman, 2010). Either practitioners feel that research is not applicable to the short deadlines and specific requirements which are common aspects of their professions, or researchers find industry unwilling to adopt new approaches. The fact of the matter is that design for emotion is suffering from a growing gap between theory and practice. As an example during the closing session of the 2010 Design and Emotion Conference, a man stood up and stated;

"I'd like to see [...] more emphasis on making design research more useful for designers. Presently it's not

so useful. It needs an extra effort to convert it to the things that make it useful for designers."

This research is aimed at answering this request by providing a quick reference guide for everyday design practitioners who wish to add an emotion focus to the user research component of their design process.

The role that emotions should play in the design of a product has been a relatively hot topic within the design community as of late. Key figures such as Desmet, Jordan, Norman and Chapman all agree that design can benefit from the development of products that are highly emotive. The Design and Emotion Society is an international organization that provides open access for researchers to place descriptions, pictures, and links for download of emotional design research tools on their website. While there exists a number of extremely useful tools, there is a lack of guidance in how to employ them in a systematic way. This study does not provide a new method or activity to *do* emotion-based user research, but rather a tool to aid in the *selection*, refocus and application of existing methods.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the beginning, the singular goal was simply to identify, create, and implement a tool which might increase the accessibility of design for emotion research for the everyday design practitioner. In this pursuit, the research took an exploratory methodology early on. This exploratory approach allowed the researcher to enter the project with limited knowledge or bias to affect the deliverable, to create a design practitioner assistive emotional design tool, but without any specific hypotheses to be tested empirically. This research based its focus on three related questions central to creating just such a tool:

1) What methods or activities are currently in use by design practitioners?

2) What are the theories from research which might be beneficial to these particular methods?

3) How might this information be assembled in such a way that it is more accessible to design practitioners?

The three questions above remained unchanged, but this exploratory, qualitative research experienced several iterative processes in which the issue being addressed was refocused to more clearly define what the tool would be and do (Robson, 2002).

RESEARCH METHODS

The methodology found in this research involved a multi-method approach; semi-structured interviews with design practitioners as well as an exploratory review of the relevant literature looking for overlapping themes. This research was guided by and attempts to explore the following topics and questions:

Assessment of the current theories and literature:

- What are emotions?
- What is the purpose of emotions?
- How do we experience emotions?
- How do emotions affect our behavior?
- How are emotions related to creativity?
- How are emotions theorized to be affected by products?
- What are the actionable theories involving emotions which can be used within the design process?

Assessment of the needs of real world design practitioners:

- What is the design process? What are its parts?
- Who are the parties involved?
- What are the research tools which are used to inform the design process?
- What methods do design researchers use to synthesize data?
- What is the purpose of data in the design process? How is it visualized?
- How can emotions be incorporated into the design process?

DESIGN PRACTITIONER INTERVIEWERS

The semi-structured interviews (O'Leary, 2004) with design practitioners informed the researcher as to the nature of current design practice. The practitioners were recruited via email through contacts within the

Arizona State University College of Design faculty. The requirements for recruitment within this study were:

1. The design practitioner must be working actively as a designer, researcher, project manager or an affiliated role.
2. They must have experience and knowledge working with a variety of projects.
3. They must also be willing to openly talk about the goals, methodologies, methods, and practices they have been involved in.

After each practitioner agreed to be a participant and signed the necessary Internal Review Board (IRB) paperwork they were asked a series of 28 questions. The questionnaire utilized open-ended questions (Robson, 2002) and focused primarily on the methods they usually employed in order to accomplish four separate tasks: gathering, synthesizing, displaying, and utilizing information during a project. The interviews were carried out one-on-one in person, over the phone, and via SKYPE.

In order to synthesize the practitioner interviews it was necessary to transcribe the interviews. At this point the transcriptions were condensed to answer specifically each question. The answers across the respondent group were then combined and tabulated per the necessity of each question in a coding technique. This process produced specific answers to each question.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The researcher quickly discovered that there are numerous theories on the purpose, origins, and evolution of human emotion. This diversity in viewpoints, combined with the exploratory nature of this research, led this review of the relevant literature to proceed in several directions. Contemporary and foundational research is synthesized from a variety of sources, all of which connect to the role of emotions in the design process. Design for emotion inherently pulls from emotion psychology, so an overview of this field's basic principles was conducted to better understand the terminology and theory essential to emotional psychology. Concurrently, descriptions of modern practices in design and business were also reviewed.

FINDINGS

Informed by this research the findings form a picture of the design process, the stakeholders involved, and the overall goal of a project. Compiling this information was paramount to understanding the environment of a real world design project.

PRODUCT DESIGN

Based upon this sample set, most design projects involve the design team being tasked with creating any of a combination of three components of a product. Illustrated in Figure 1 the components or elements of a product can be differentiated as: Aesthetics, Function, and Core. While Aesthetics and Function may not need much explanation the component of Core is a bit more abstract. The “Core” of a product has to do with the intangible aspects of a product such as its brand, identity, or personality. The goal of any design team is to successfully produce a product in which these components resonate with a user.

Components of a Product

Figure 1: Components of a Product as seen by a design team.

DESIGN TEAM

A design team can vary in size as well as specific skill sets of those individual. Regardless of the hierarchy, for most projects one individual within the design team serves as the cog, acting as the administrator of the team. This individual is usually the design researcher or someone who has the most hands on connections to the whole process, but need not be the team lead or project manager. The design researcher’s roles include: researcher, user advocate, designer, and

manager. His or her respective responsibilities include but are not limited to project recruitment, respondent observation, design team inspiration, project planning, design team alignment, data gathering /translation, and informant. The researcher is the individual who is responsible for ensuring that the final design of a product answers not only the initial goals of the project but also resonates with the end user. As this individual is usually in charge of planning research strategies they would likely benefit most from the assistive tool produced from this research.

THE DESIGN PROCESS

A major role of the researcher during the design process is managing the communication of data to the necessary stakeholders. This text designates the design process as the course by which a design project is carried from initial problem as put forth by the client (or management), all the way to the final concept delivered back to the client. Swann (2002) describes design as a multi-staged iterative process. If looking at the design process in terms of the flow of data through a project, it can be simplified down to three distinct stages: Gather, Synthesize, and Utilize.

The design researcher takes on a lead role during the data gathering portion of a project. To understand how best to assist the design research it is necessary to further analyze this particular stage of the process.

Data Flow During the Design Process

Figure 2: The flow of data during the design process is an iterative process.

DATA GATHERING

During a data gathering stage of a project the researcher and/or fellow team members may use any

variety of different methods and activities. Within the interview transcriptions, there were four categories of data gathering methods which design practitioners might utilize: **Qualitative, Interactive, Ethnographic and Quantitative.**

Qualitative:	Interactive:	Ethnographic:	Quantitative:
Feedback Sessions	Collage Creation	Experience Through Doing	Attribute Study
Interviews	Word Association	Scenarios	Biomechanical Testing
Iterative Prototyping	Journey Diary	Shop Along Studies	Ergonomic Testing
	Buddy Diary	6 Real People	
	Tactile Bags		
	Consumer Brainstorming		

Table 1: Practitioner Methods.

These methods are used specifically to help kick start projects and push the later design processes along. These methods produce outputs which, after being synthesized, inspire the design team and allow them to be more creative by identifying respondent's aspirations and goals. Additionally, their output empowers the design team to edit their concepts because they understand how to resonate with users and predict their future likings. This process is similar to determining the range of acceptance with which a design team is able to work within. To further expound, these methods identify information which is pertinent to the alignment of the design team to the deep, sub-surface issues that motivate people. Data gathering's sole purpose is to produce information that will allow the design team to learn through empathy. Within these methods respondents are empowered with the ability to communicate their thoughts and feelings, which allows the design team to fully design to this user group.

Several of the activities used by current practitioners force the respondent to activate and retrieve information found in different portions of their memory. Koll, Wallpach, and Kreuzer (2010) examined these parts of memory as they relate to how a user views a product. Specifically, they investigated the semantic/associative memory system and the episodic memory system. These different systems and the types of knowledge stored therein are illustrated in graphical form in Figure 3.

Semantic Memory: In this framework, what some conceive of as separate semantic and associative memory systems are one in the same. This semantic/associative system contains mostly verbal facts about a product, divided up into categorical and conceptual knowledge in the form of abstract, context-free information and general facts (Koll, Walpach, & Kreuzer, 2010). Since semantic memory develops via rational thinking, it makes sense to conclude that the consumer's memories stored in the semantic system are encoded in symbols, words, and numbers.

Episodic Memory: The episodic memory system is made up of more detailed, context specific information. Product knowledge stored in episodic memory is often tied to personal experiences with a specific product (Koll, Walpach, & Kreuzer, 2010). Insights into episodic memory and procedural knowledge can clarify the strong bonds between brands and consumers. It is conceivable that knowledge of product related episodic memories could inform the designer as to a user's motivations and goals involving the product.

Episodic and Semantic memory are tapped and retrieved via different pathways. Koll, Wallpach, and Kreuzer (2010) hypothesize that there are two types of retrieval systems: the declarative system which is largely an explicit form of fact recall, and the procedural system which is largely made up of implicit opinions and knowledge that the user may not be consciously aware of. These memory retrieval systems account for the fact that consumers process and retrieve both verbal and nonverbal product knowledge on a conscious as well as on an unconscious level.

Declarative/procedural dichotomy: The declarative and procedural knowledge systems are on two different ends of a memory spectrum that differentiates between conscious and unconscious knowledge processing and retrieval. Declarative memory contains intentionally or consciously acquired, stored, and retrieved knowledge. This sort of knowledge is easily acquired through explicit means; simply asking respondent direct questions will likely produce useful answers. Procedural knowledge, on the other hand, consists of skills or abilities

consumers acquire non-reflectively (typically via prior experience) and apply without conscious effort. This sort of knowledge is best assessed through more implicit means.

Using the descriptions above as a guide, the data gathering methods identified by the design practitioners were evaluated and sorted into their most likely storage and retrieval systems. The color designation of blue and yellow can be seen in Table 1. Note that not all methods fell into a designated category.

Figure 3: Koll, Wallpach, and Kreuzer (2010)

Theoretical Framework

The findings summarize the relevant information regarding who is involved in a design process, the process itself and the theory behind the research methods which lead to producing a final product. It is now necessary to take that information and apply it through a design for emotion lens.

Adapted from his earlier work, Desmet (2008) has created a basic model of product emotion which states that emotions stem from appraisals of concerns and the object of focus. This model is a simple and easily understood way in which designers can make sense of human emotions and their relationship to the products in the world today. To expound upon this model Desmet uses a chart in which the nine sources of product emotion are described in detail as three different sets of appraisals. A modified version of his appraisal table combined with the “Components of a Product” Chart can be found in Figure 4. Desmet breaks down these appraisals by combining a person’s attitudes, goals and standards to the product,

its use and the negative/positive consequences of interaction.

This appraisal method can aid researchers in understanding the emotional perceptions a person has of a particular product, but it can still be confusing. To make it more useful it is necessary to take the earlier sorted practitioner activities and map them onto this diagram. Figure 4 depicts both how common data gathering methods map onto Desmet’s appraisal diagram and what memory systems are most likely to be involved in a user’s report of his or her attitudes, standards, and goals around a product.

Figure 4: Modified Product Emotion (Desmet 2008) combined with the components of a product as seen by a design team.

The model found in Figure 5 is the basis of the tool produced from this research to assist during the data gathering stage of the design process. By mapping the specific practitioner methods and insights from the practitioner interviews onto this model it was possible to create the final tool.

Figure 5: Memory retrieval mapped onto Product Emotion model.

DELIVERABLE: EMOTION TAPPING FRAMEWORK

The practitioner interviews and literature review worked together to inform a final decision making framework for designing for emotion: an *Emotion Tapping* framework. This tool is located in the appendix of this paper. It is meant to aid design practitioners by guiding them in the selection and focus of user research methods during data gather. Additionally, design for emotion researchers can use this as a guide to focus their own research using and developing methods for the design field. This matrix is not meant to be an end-all tool for practitioners seeking to take advantage of the benefits of an emotion-based design approach, but rather is poised as a guide to help focus their efforts and make project planning more effective. It does this specifically by providing a quick reference guide for practitioners to build upon.

The Emotion Tapping framework puts the elements of assembled research into a task-oriented format which practitioners will find more useful. It functions by asking the practitioner to first look at each of nine different segments of knowledge to be gained from the diagram and judge which segments of knowledge they wish to obtain. Next, by taking into account the specified research methods and focus the practitioner can plan a product component-specific activity. Below are a few examples of how the Emotion Tapping Framework might be used.

Example 1

Project Brief: Design the appearance of a current model of cell phone.

Focus: Activities should be primarily quick surface level judgments of the appearance of current product.

Proposed Methods: Interviews, feedback session or product attribute studies.

Example 2

Project Brief: Design the user interaction of a conceptual prescription drug management device.

Proposed Methods: Interviews, feedback sessions, collage creation, journey diary, or scenarios.

Focus: Activities should focus primarily on obtaining the goals that the user hopes to accomplish by completing a task.

Example 3

Project Brief: Design the concept for Wounded Warriors facility.

Proposed Methods: Collage Creation, Journey Diary, Experience Though Doing, Scenarios, Shop Along.

Focus: Activities should focus primarily on obtaining the standards with which the respondent feels their life must change to be.

CONCLUSION

The Emotion Tapping Framework would most benefit the generative stages after data has been gathered from the field. Practitioners capable of obtaining more substantial data would be more likely to emotionally influence the later stages of the design process, advocate for the aspirations of the user and ultimately lead a project to innovative final concepts which are more attuned with the emotional needs of the end user. The task and product characteristic orientation of this chart is more in line with the needs of the designers based upon the insights generated during the interviews.

PROPOSED BENEFITS AND ARGUMENTS FOR AN EMOTIONAL DESIGN PROCESS IN PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

The major premise of this applied project was that a systematic approach to design research loosely based within emotional psychology would be far better than traditional methods. Central to this argument is the belief that traditional methods of product development have at their core a focus which is overly centered on creating a solution which fulfills a specific function, ultimately ignoring the emotional needs of the user. Often, the work being done in design may not be what is most beneficial to the end user and in this sense inefficient. The proposed benefits of an emotion-based research process are:

- Emotions aid collaboration by serving as a bridge across stakeholder language barriers by serving as a common language.
- The final concept would benefit from a design team which is inspirationally informed to create solutions for users with whom they have a more emotional connection.
- Current concepts could be deconstructed to their more abstract emotional components as a means

by which to induce cognitive dissonance within the design team and lead to paradigm shifts in a product's design.

COMMON LANGUAGE

Design is a creative act involving a collaborative group of individuals. A group environment utilizing many points of view is far better at producing creative and intelligent thoughts (Csikszentmihalyi, 1996; John-Steiner, 2000; Salomon, 1993). Within the design context these groups of individuals include but are not limited to: the design team, user group or research subjects, and a third party client (or management).

When an interdisciplinary group of individuals come together in this context they bring with them their skills, knowledge, and specialized language. In this context, Gerhard Fischer (2004) refers to these differences as distances. He also outlines several important distances which must be taken into account during collaboration:

- **Temporal** (across time), requiring support for asynchronous, indirect, long-term communication (Fischer et al., 1992; Olson, Olson, Storrosten, Carter, Herbsleb, & Rueter, 1996)
- **Conceptual** (across different communities of practice), requiring support for common ground and shared understanding (Fischer, 2001; Resnick, 1991);
- **Technological** (between persons and artifacts), requiring knowledge-based, domain-oriented systems (Fischer, 1994; Fischer, 2004; Terveen, 1995)

If a collaborative team is to function optimally as a creative team they must be able to bridge these distances. Human emotions lend themselves naturally as a means by which all partners can communicate. A recent study by Professor Sophie Scott of the University College of London sought to establish whether or not certain emotions are universal. The study involved two different culture groups: one in Britain and one in Namibia and used sounds associated with emotions such as happiness, anger, fear, sadness, disgust and surprise (Sauter, Eisner, Ekman, & Scott, 2009). The findings from this research suggest that all humans share basic

emotions such as amusement, anger, fear and sadness and vocalize them in similar ways recognizable across cultural and geographical boundaries. Additionally, previous research has shown that facial expressions of these basic emotions are recognized across a wide range of cultures (Ekman & Friesen, 1971).

Emotions are how humans interact with the world, and by utilizing them to communicate between the different parties involved in a project, the entire group is able to draw upon a common body of knowledge to communicate their respective views or understand the views of others. Alternatively, not using an emotional communication language within a collaborative group has the potential to be very costly. The distances as outlined by Fischer can be detrimental to all parties involved and have the capacity of creating project infighting and can destroy a project.

INSPIRATIONALLY INFORMED DESIGN

Design teams, clients, users and extraneous project partners are all human. As mentioned above, to communicate ideas between all of these groups it is necessary to utilize a language which is easily understood by all parties involved. Emotions lend themselves to this role as well as serving the role of creating empathy and inspiration in the design team.

“Empathic Design” as described by Rayport and Leonard (1997) is a technique by which designers attempt to evaluate the needs of a potential user group by examining a product from the user's perspective. A major argument of empathic design is that:

The problem is customers' ability to guide the development of new products and services is limited by their experience and their ability to imagine and describe possible innovations. How can companies identify needs that customers themselves may not recognize? How can designers develop ways to meet those needs, if even in the course of extensive market research, customers never mention their desires because they assume those desires can't be fulfilled. (Leonard & Rayport, 1997, p. 3)

Utilizing an emotion-based research process has the potential to empower respondents to openly evaluate their own perceptions and standards in terms which are inspirational to the design teams and enable designers to better comprehend and more fully empathize with abstract emotional needs.

GROUNDING DECONSTRUCTION

As in empathic design, sometimes design teams also have a difficult time moving past what is outside of their own experiences and their ability to imagine possible innovations. The existing embodiment of a product might prevent a design team from reimagining a product outside of making only superficial changes.

To be freed of the confines of this embodiment it is necessary to deconstruct the existing solution to more abstract terms. In this deconstruction process, so long as there is a structure by which to ground the emotional components, a new innovative conceptual model of the product can be created. This approach may be likened to creating nonsense of an established paradigm and then through the use of cognitive dissonance re-constituting that nonsense into a new paradigm.

In her presentation at the 7th Annual International Design and Emotion Conference, Amy Bickerton (2010) expounded on the role of nonsense and cognitive dissonance. She pointed out that, *Cognitive dissonance-the flood of emotion and intellectual stimulation that accompanies the unexpected and seemingly illogical moments in life is a powerful paradigm of human psychology. People strive to create meaning in their lives, and designers can tap into this powerful rhetorical opportunity through the use of nonsense that disorganizes in order to create a fresh model of meaning and coherence. Nonsense-and the organization, disorganization, and reorganization that it requires-can disrupt expectations to create transformative experiences.* (Bickerton, 2010, p. 11)

An emotion-based research strategy is meant to gather emotional information from respondents and effectively deconstruct that data into a structured informative inspirational output. It is meant to serve as a concept creation strategy, centered on the

understanding of the current emotional responses and desires of modern users. Overall, if this shift in design development were to occur it would better align current product solutions with the needs of users as well as open the door for new concepts which had previously not been thought of.

FUTURE WORK:

The framework informed by this research is currently being used as a basis to design several emotion focused research methods which ultimately make up a larger research strategy. This strategy also titled *Emotion Tapping*, consist of participatory interviews, guided exercise research techniques, an emotion focused brainstorming activity for generating product concepts and communication network for sharing as well as recording outcomes from this process. Additionally, to fully meet the needs of design practitioners work is being carried out to evolve this process into an iPad application (Cathexis). The hope is that this format will be beneficial because it can be widely distributed to really delve into how individuals feel about any product they use. The interview structure and technological format encourages the product user/respondent to share his or her emotional experiences around different aspects of a product that they likely would not share in the more traditional research mediums such as focus groups or interviews. This tool then synthesizes the user's responses to create a visual representation of the respondent's emotional appraisal of a product which can easily be converted into new ideas and revisions.

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Appendix:
Emotion Tapping Framework

	Attitudes <i>What the current product is</i>	Goals <i>What the product should be</i>	Standards <i>What the deliverable must be/do</i>
Product	What does it look like?	What should it look like?	What must it be?
Focus:	The visceral emotions evoked by the product's appearance.	The emotions a person wishes to experience from the interacting with the product.	The emotions tied to the basic properties a product MUST have.
Methods:	Interviews, Attribute studies	Feedback Sessions, Collage Creation, Word Association, Attribute Study	Collage Creation, Word Association, Journey Diary, Scenarios, Experience Through Doing, Shop Along Studies
Usage	How does it function?	How should it function?	What must it do?
Focus:	The emotions evoked by what the product does and what it's like to use at that moment.	The emotion a respondent hopes to experience during usage.	The emotions tied to the functions a product MUST do.
Methods:	Interviews, Feedback Sessions, Attribute Studies	Interviews, feedback sessions, collage creation, journey diaries, or scenarios	Collage Creation, Word Association, Journey Diary, Scenarios, Experience Through Doing, Shop Along Studies
Consequence	What it is like to possess?	What SHOULD it be like to possess?	What MUST it be like to possess?
Focus:	The emotions evoked through ownership of a product.	The emotions a user hopes to experience as a result of owning a product.	The emotions experienced when a product does or does not produce desired outcome.
Methods:	Interviews, Feedback Sessions, Attribute Studies	Interviews, feedback sessions, collage creation, journey diaries, or scenarios	Collage Creation, Word Association, Journey Diary, Scenarios, Experience Through Doing, Shop Along Studies

Figure 5: The Emotion Tapping Chart is beneficial to design practitioners. It combines the practitioner methods, memory retrieval and activation, and design for emotion research into a quick reference guide to assist in the planning stages prior to beginning data gathering. It's product component and task orientation fits into the needs of design practitioners.